

Nucleophiles, nucleophilicity and relationship between nucleophilicity and basicity

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Abstract : The concept of nucleophilicity and electrophilicity are most useful in understanding polar reactions. Polar reactions proceed by the movement of pairs of electrons from areas of high electron density, called nucleophiles to areas of low electron density called electrophiles or from filled orbitals to empty orbitals. Nucleophiles also control the rate of bimolecular substitution reaction. Certain aspects of this concept, however; not been treated with sufficient clarity. The aim of this write up is to clarify these aspects and to report a comparative study about nucleophilicity and basicity.

Keywords : Nucleophilicity, basicity, solvent.

Introduction

A nucleophile is a nucleus loving species and is defined as a compound that has a relatively high energy pair of electrons available to make a new bond with an electron deficient species (electrophile). A nucleophilic atom may be neutral or negatively charged. Depending on the nature of donating electron pair, nucleophiles are classified in three ways¹.

- Lone pair nucleophiles : These types of nucleophiles contain atoms with lone pair of electrons. Examples of this kind are alcohols (ROH), alkoxides (RO⁻), halides (X⁻), thiols (RSH), phosphines (R₃P).
- σ bond nucleophiles : Nucleophiles contain a σ bond between a nonmetal and metal. The electrons of the nonmetal-metal bond are used to form a bond between the nonmetal and the electrophile.
- Pi bond nucleophiles : Such nucleophiles use the pair of electrons in a π bond, usually a C=C bond. These form a σ bond between one of the atoms in the π -bond and the electrophilic atom. The π -bonds of simple C=C are weakly nucleophilic but the π -bonds that are directly attached to hetero atoms like enols and enolates (C=C-OH, C=C-O), enol ethers (C=C-OR) and enamines (C=C-NR₂) are much nucleophiles.

Nucleophiles are also classified as hard, soft and borderline. In polar reactions nucleophiles react with

electrophiles. The attraction between electrophiles and nucleophiles depends on the electrostatic attraction between two opposite charges of the two and the orbital overlap between the HOMO of the nucleophile and the LUMO of the electrophile. Nucleophiles containing small, electronegative atoms (have higher charge density) are called hard nucleophiles and nucleophiles containing larger atoms, diffuse orbitals or are uncharged are called soft nucleophiles. Some nucleophiles fall in between the two are called borderline. Hard nucleophiles have low energy HOMO whereas soft nucleophiles have high energy HOMO. Some common hard, soft and borderline nucleophiles are shown in the following table (Table 1)².

Table 1. Hard, soft and borderline nucleophiles

Hard nucleophiles	Borderline	Soft nucleophiles
F ⁻ , HO ⁻ , RO ⁻ , SO ₄ ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , H ₂ O, ROH,	N ₃ ⁻ , CN ⁻ , RNH ₂ , RRNH, Br ⁻	I ⁻ , RS ⁻ , RSe ⁻ , S ²⁻ , RSH, RSR', R ₃ P,
ROR', RCOR', NH ₃ , RMgBr, RLi		alkenes, aromatic rings

Ambident nucleophiles : These are species which have more than one nucleophilic centers (the term 'amb' means on both sides). The examples are CN⁻, NO₂⁻, CNO⁻, NCS⁻, SO₃²⁻ etc. A typical example is the CN⁻ group : both carbon and nitrogen have a lone electron pair and so CN⁻ can attack a substrate with either atom. An alkyl iodide in aqueous ethanol forms mainly alkyl cyanide with KCN but yields alkyl isocyanide with AgCN. This

can be explained by the principle of hard and soft acid bases. The carbon atom will be the softer and the nitrogen atom the harder end of the nucleophile. Thus the electrophiles which attack cyanide ion on nitrogen will be the harder ones and the electrophiles which attack on carbon will be softer one.

The carbon atom bearing the halogen atom in alkyl halide undergoing S_N2 reaction is soft electrophile; thus it is appropriate for cyanide to react from the soft end 'C' of the ion (Scheme 1)

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

But when a silver ion is present, the halide ion is attracted by the Ag^+ to form a carbocation, for which the reaction proceeds through S_N1 mode. Carbocation is a hard electrophile and therefore the cyanide ion should react from the harder end of the ion i.e. through the N centre (Scheme 2).

Similarly, silver nitrite ($AgNO_2$) forms a mixture of alkyl nitrite ($R-O-NO$) and nitro alkane, $R-NO_2$, on heating with an alkyl halide. The formation of nitrite follows S_N2 pathway whereas that of nitro alkane S_N1 .

Enolate ion of acetoacetic ester, an ambident carbanions, forms C-alkyl derivative with an alkyl iodide but an O-alkyl compound with an α -chloro ether by S_N2 and S_N1 mechanism respectively. The carbanions attacks the partially positive carbon of $R-I$ in the former, whereas the more negative oxygen in the oxanion attacks the car-

bonium ion of the α -chloro ether (Scheme 3).

Nucleophilic strength :

The relative strengths of nucleophiles depend on the following facts.

- A species with a negative charge is a stronger nu-

cleophile than a similar neutral species.

- Nucleophilicity decreases from left to right in the periodic table, through which the electronegativity of the atom also decreases.

More electronegative elements have more tightly held non bonding electrons thus reluctant towards electron donation.

- Nucleophilicity of the atoms increases down the periodic table, due to the increase in size and polarizability.
- *Effect of counter cation* : The order of reactivity of halide ions towards the reaction of $(n)\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OBn}$ in acetone solution is $\text{I}^{-} > \text{Br}^{-} > \text{Cl}^{-}$ if LiX is used but the order becomes $\text{I}^{-} < \text{Br}^{-} < \text{Cl}^{-}$ if $[(n)\text{C}_4\text{H}_9]_4\text{N}^{+}\text{X}^{-}$ is used³. The reason comes in the following way. Li^{+} is smaller in size and forms a tight ion pairs with the anions. Smaller anions have higher charge density than that of larger ones, for which smaller the halide ions stronger the ion pairing and the less reactive the nucleophiles. On the other hand the large quarternary ammonium ion with its charge shielded by the bulky alkyl groups, forms only very loose ion pairs. Thus in presence of $[(n)\text{C}_4\text{H}_9]_4\text{N}^{+}$ the halide ions are relatively free and the ion with greater charge density (smaller ion) will have higher nucleophilicity than that with lower charge density (larger ion).

Similarly the nucleophilicity order of F^{-} depends on the size of the counter cation. Larger the counter cation the ion pairing becomes weak hence higher will be the nucleophilicity of F^{-} . Thus the nucleophilicity order : $\text{CsF} > \text{RbF} > \text{KF} > \text{NaF} > \text{LiF}$.

- *Effect of solvent* :

The nucleophilicity order of anions in general depends very much on the degree of solvation. In protic solvent anions are subject to strong interactions with solvent. Hard (charge/radius is high) nucleophiles are more strongly solvated by protic solvents than soft (charge/radius is low) nucleophiles hence in protic polar solvent (like MeOH , H_2O) soft anions will have higher nucleophilicity.

In the absence of protic solvents the relative nu-

cleophilicity of anions changes. Hard anions will have higher nucleophilicity than the soft anions because of the greater charge density of the hard anions.

Several investigators have attempted to establish a relative order of nucleophilic reactivities of which Swain-Scott equation⁴ is simple and convenient. Their model was solvolysis of methyl bromide in water at 25 °C. The rates of SN^2 reactions between CH_3Br and various nucleophiles were used in their equation : $\log k/k_0 = sn$ where k is the rate constant for the reaction of a particular nucleophile with a substrate, k_0 is the rate constant for the reaction of the same substrate with water, n is the nucleophilicity constant and s is a parameter characteristic of the substrate. It is a measure of its sensitivity towards various nucleophiles. By definition, therefore, $n = 0$ for water and $s = 1.0$ for CH_3Br . Relative nucleophilic reactivities can be calculated from this equation for limited range of experimental conditions. n values, given in the literature, are a useful guide for substitution reactions at a saturated carbon atom in water or water-organic solvent mixtures. Its application is not wide as s values are available only for a small number of substrates.

Relationship between nucleophilicity and basicity :

Any electron pair donor is a nucleophile when it reacts at a comparatively electron deficient site. This is similar to the definition of a base, as bases also have unshared electron pairs. The terms nucleophile and base may be used to describe exactly the same species participating in different reactions.

Following example illustrate this point.

But there are important differences between the two. The nucleophilicity of a compound is measured by the rate of bimolecular nucleophilic substitution i.e. by determining how reactive it is towards CH_3Br (SN^2 process) in water at 25 °C. However the basicity of a base is measured by the position of the following equilibrium (i.e. by the equilibrium constant K_b).

$$K_b = [BH^+]/[B][H^+]$$

Basicity affects the positions of equilibria and nucleophilicity affects the rate of reactions so basicity is a thermodynamic property and nucleophilicity is a kinetic property.

Again CH_3Br is uncharged, relatively large, and has a relatively high energy LUMO. On the other hand low charge H^+ has low energy LUMO. Because of the differences, some bases are poor nucleophiles, and vice versa. Nucleophilicity and basicity do correlate of a series of compounds in which the same atom is the nucleophile, e.g.

However, the nucleophilicity-basicity correlation is not useful for comparison of atoms down a family of the periodic table. As atomic number increases nucleophilicity increases but basicity decreases⁵. For example,

From left to right nucleophilicity increases but basicity decreases. The explanation comes in the following way. In nucleophilic attack on the saturated carbon atom, the

nucleophile must donate its electrons to the σ^* orbital of C-X bond. Whereas for a species to act as a base it must donate its electron pair to 1s orbital of H^+ . We may express the reaction of a nucleophile Nu^- (negatively charge) with a cationic electrophile E^+ in the following way (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

Now the following three interactions are considered (Fig. 1).

From the above diagram it is concluded that the energy gain is greatest when the two orbitals are same in energy and least when they are very far apart in energy. Now the M.O. interaction of RS^- and RO^- with H^+ and C-X may be considered in the following way² (Fig. 2).

The higher energy ($3sp^3$) lone-pair electrons on sulfur overlap better with the high energy σ^* orbital of the C-X bond than do the lower energy ($2sp^3$) lone-pair electrons on oxygen because the higher energy of the sulfur electrons brings closer in energy to the C-X σ^* orbital.

Down a group of the periodic table, the HOMO of the nucleophilic atoms increases and becomes closer to the σ^* orbital of C-X bond and hence nucleophilicity increases. The explanation comes in other way also. The useful qualitative approach for explaining the basicity vs nucleophilicity is the HSAB concept. This tells that hard nucleophiles prefer hard electrophiles where as soft nucleophiles prefer soft electrophiles. The C^+ centre is softer

Fig. 1

Fig. 2. M.O. interaction of RO^- and RS^{-2} .

than H^+ , the larger atoms are softer and hence prefer 'C' centre.

Bisulphite ion shows rather interesting dependence of basicity and nucleophilicity on the atoms with in a single ion. Charge is delocalized over the oxygen and sulfur atom. The more basic oxygen atom typically reacts with a proton and the more nucleophilic sulphur atom typically reacts at a carbon atom (Scheme 5).

α -Effect :

There is exception to the generalization that nucleo-

philicity parallels basicity for systems that react via the same atom. An electronegative atom having unshared electron pairs such as 'O' or 'N' bonded to a nucleophilic atom, makes it a stronger nucleophile than one without such atoms. For example, the hydroperoxide ion, HOO^- reacts nearly 35 times faster than the HO^- ion with benzyl bromide in aqueous acetone (1 : 1) at 25 °C, though HO^- is a much stronger base than HOO^- . NH_2OH , NH_2NH_2 , R_2S_2 , ^-OCl behaves similarly. This behaviour is known as α -effect. This is explained by considering the Frontier Molecular Orbitals of NH_2NH_2 . The two 1ps on the adjacent nitrogens of hydrazine interact with each other as shown by the M.O. diagram⁶. As a result of interaction the energy of the HOMO has been raised relative to the energy of the HOMO in the absence of the other lone pair. The higher energy HOMO of NH_2NH_2 can interact favourably with the low lying LUMO (σ^*) of a relatively soft nucleophile such as an alkyl halide. The basicity is not increased, it is actually decreased because of the electron withdrawing effect of the second nitrogen (Fig. 3).

Steric effect :

Nucleophilicity is much more sensitive to steric effects than base strength. MeO^- is a weak base but strong nucleophile, $^tBuO^-$ is a strong base but weak nucleophile. To serve as a nucleophile, an ion or molecule must get in close to a carbon atom to attack it. Bulky groups on the nucleophile hinder this close approach. $^tBuO^-$ ion has three methyl groups that hinder any close approach to a carbon atom. Therefore MeO^- is a stronger nucleophile than $^tBuO^-$. Steric hindrance has little effect on basicity

Scheme 5

Fig. 3. Partial M.O. diagram of NH_2NH_2 .⁶

because basicity involves attack on an unhindered triethylamine (I) is less reactive than quinuclidine (II) towards methyl iodide in nitromethane solvent at 25 °C in forming quaternary ammonium compounds⁷. Both are tertiary amines and approximately of the same basicity. In triethyl amine, the alkyl groups (capable of free rotation around N–C bonds) shield the nitrogen physically from attack by the partially positive group of $\text{CH}_3\text{-Br}$. In quinuclidine, the nitrogen occupies bridge head position. The attached group being in fixed positions can not behave similarly in alkyl groups in triethyl amine and its nitrogen is more exposed than the nitrogen in triethyl amine.

Some important points¹ :

- Second row elements or heavier species and the very stable carbanion are good nucleophiles and poor base. Br^- , I^- , R_2S^- , R_3P , CN^- , malonate anions, R_2CuLi belongs in this class.
- First row unhindered species and moderately stable carbanions are both good nucleophiles and good bases. Unhindered RO^- , R_2N^- , R_3N , enamines, simple enolates, $\text{R-C}\equiv\text{C}^-$, Cl^- are in this class.
- First row, hindered species and unstabilised carbanions are poor nucleophiles and good bases, $^t\text{BuO}^-$, $^i\text{Pr}_2\text{NLi}$, (LDA), $(\text{Me}_3\text{Si})_2\text{NK}$ (KHMDs), $^i\text{Pr}_2\text{Net}$ (Hunig's base), amidines and guanidines such as DBN, DBU and TMG are in this class. NaH and KH are also in this class.

DBU

DBN

TMG

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